

Extractive Photometric Determination of Copper(II) and Stepwise Formation Constants of its Complexes with N-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)- and N-(4-Methyl-phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide

S. P. BAG* and B. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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N-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)- and N-(4-methyl-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide forms brown complexes with copper(II) in the pH range 5.0-8.0 and 4.0-10.0, respectively. The chloroform extracts of the complexes have the absorption maxima at 440 and 430 nm and obey Beer's law from 0.5 to 5.0 ppm. The metal-ligand ratio in the complexes is 1 : 2. The molar absorptivities and Sandell's sensitivities are 8.00×10^4 , 6.60×10^4 mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.008, 0.010 μ g Cu²⁺ per cm². Sn²⁺, Pd²⁺ and Os⁶⁺ interfere in the determination. The stability constants (log K) are 8.60, 8.11 and 9.86, 9.14 by different photometric methods at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

IN the present investigation an attempt has been made to find some selective reagents for copper with sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms. The effect on sensitivity with change of functional groups has also been investigated. The reagents synthesized are highly selective for the determination of copper and superior to other existing methods in selectivity. The method was extended for the determination of copper in B.S. white metal, ferro-titanium and pyrite ore. The stepwise formation constants k_1 and k_2 of the complexes CuL_1^+ and CuL_2 , respectively have been evaluated following the graphical extrapolation method of Leden¹ and Yatsimirskii²⁻⁴. The overall formation constant of the copper complexes has also been evaluated by Harvey-Manning⁵ method.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer and a Spektromom 204 with 1 cm quartz cells were used for measurement of absorbance.

The reagents were prepared by Porter's⁶ method. N-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide (reagent I) was prepared by refluxing *p*-anisidine (2 mole), α -picoline (1 mole) and sulphur powder (1.5 mole). The thio compound was isolated by repeated extraction of the oily mass with petroleum ether (40-60°). The petroleum ether was evaporated and the solid yellow mass was crystallized twice from absolute ethanol, yield 20% (based on α -picoline), m.p. 95°. (Found : C, 63.68 ; H, 4.56 ; N, 11.60 ; S, 13.20, Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$; C, 63.93 ; H, 4.92 ; N, 11.48 ; S, 13.11%).

N-(4-Methyl-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide (reagent-II) was similarly prepared by refluxing *p*-toluidine (2 mole), α -picoline (1 mole) and sulphur powder (1.5 mole), m.p. 97°. (Found : C, 68.18 ;

H, 4.71 ; N, 11.96 ; S, 14.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}$; C, 68.42 ; H, 5.26 ; N, 12.28 ; S, 14.04%).

A standard solution of Cu²⁺ was prepared from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R., E. Merck) and standardised against electrolytic copper wire by the iodometric method.

Freshly prepared reagent solutions (I, 0.1%) and (II, 0.2%) in chloroform were used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra :

The absorption spectra of 6.30×10^{-5} M Cu²⁺ with reagents I and II showed that the complexes have absorption maxima at 440 and 430 nm, respectively in chloroform.

Effect of pH and reagent concentrations :

The complexes showed constant colour intensity from pH 5.0 to 8.0 for reagent I and from pH 4.0 to 10.0 for reagent II. The optimum concentration where the absorbance remains constant is from 2.0 to 3.5 ml of 0.1% reagent I and 1.0 to 5.0 ml of 0.2% reagent II in chloroform for the aqueous : non-aqueous phase ratio of 1 : 1. The absorbance was then measured against reagent blank at 440 and 430 nm, respectively.

Beer's law, optimum range, sensitivity and photometric error :

The colour systems obeyed Beer's law from 0.5 to 5.0 ppm Cu²⁺ with reagents I and II. The Ringbom⁷ plot showed that the optimum range was 1.0 to 5.0 ppm for reagents I and II. The percent relative error⁸ in this range was 2.72.

The molar absorptivity was found to be 8.00×10^8 and 6.60×10^8 l.mole⁻¹cm⁻¹. The sensitivity according to Sandell's⁹ definition was 0.008 and 0.010 $\mu\text{g Cu}^{2+}/\text{cm}^2$ for the two reagents, respectively.

Composition of the complexes :

The composition of the complexes in solution was ascertained by the Job's¹⁰ method of continuous variation and by the mole ratio¹¹ method. Job's method was used with equimolar solutions (7.86×10^{-4} M) of Cu^{2+} and ligand. In the mole ratio method a constant metal ion concentration (1 ml 1.57×10^{-3} M) was used. The composition of the complexes was found to be 1 : 2 with respect to metal : ligand.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of foreign ions on the determination of Cu^{2+} was studied by adding them separately and extracting the complexes with chloroform following the recommended procedure. It was observed that 200 ppm Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Ir^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , W^{6+} , V^{4+} and 400 ppm SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , F^- , acetate, citrate, oxalate, tartrate, thiocyanate have no adverse effect on the determination of 4 ppm Cu^{2+} . Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Ti^{4+} can be masked by tartaric acid. Sn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Os^{6+} and EDTA interfere seriously.

Application of the methods in ferrous, non-ferrous alloys and ores :

Cu^{2+} was determined from ferro-titanium (British Standard 434/2), white metal (British Standard 8d) and pyrite (British Standard 44nG) following the recommended procedure. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN ALLOYS AND ORE

Samples	*Results (Cu^{2+} found)	
	Reagent-I	Reagent-II
1. B.S. 248/2 ferro-titanium Ti=40.95%, Al=7.45%, C=0.04%, Cu=1.21%, Si=8.87%, Mn=1.18%, Nb+Ta=0.07%	1.19%	1.20%
2. B.S. 8d white metal Cu=8.0%, Zn=0.085%, Sn= 86.10%, Pb=3.26%, Sb=6.60%, Cd=0.27%	2.96%	2.97%
3. B.S. 44 nG pyrite ore Cu=0.84%, S=47.0%, Fe=41.2%	0.88%	0.84%

* Results of the average of three different determinations were taken.

Degree of dissociation and stepwise formation constants :

The degree of dissociation, α , and the dissociation constant, K , were calculated from the equation of Harvey and Manning. The dissociation constants were found to be 2.22×10^{-9} and 1.48×10^{-9} with reagents I and II, respectively. So the overall stability constants are 4.51×10^{10} and 6.76×10^8 .

Evaluation of metal-ligand formation constants :

Leden's method : In this method the degree of formation (ϕ) of a complex system is utilised for the evaluation of stepwise formation constants. The degree of formation is defined as the ratio of overall concentration of metal ion C_M to the equilibrium concentration of free metal ion $[M]$,

$$\phi = \frac{C_M}{[M]} = 1 + \sum_1^N \beta[L]^N \quad (1)$$

In the present system where the ratio of Cu to ligand is 1 : 2, ϕ reduces to

$$\phi = 1 + k_1[L] + k_1k_2[L]^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

The coefficients k_1 , k_2 of the variable $[L]$ are obtained by constructing suitable auxiliary functions (ψ_1 , ψ_2) and extrapolating these to zero value of the variable.

$$\text{Thus, } \psi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = k_1 + k_1k_2[L]$$

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = k_1 = \beta_1 = 9.20 \times 10^4 \text{ and } 2.80 \times 10^4$$

for reagents I and II (Fig. 1)

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_2 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi_1 - k_1}{[L]} = k_1k_2 = \beta_2 = 4.00 \times 10^8 \text{ and } 1.30 \times 10^8$$

for reagents I and II (Fig. 2)

Fig. 1. Plots of ψ_1 for Cu^{2+} complex from Leden's method with reagents I and II.

Fig. 2. Plots of ψ_2 for Cu^{2+} complex from Leden's method with reagents I and II.

Yatsimirskii's method : The mean molar extinction coefficient of the species ML_n ($n \geq 0$) and L which absorb strongly at a definite wavelength is given by eq. (3)

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{A}{(C_M + [L])l} \quad (3)$$

where the terms have their usual meaning. In the present system $M:L=1:2$. The equation then simplifies to eq. (4)

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{\epsilon_1 k_1 [L] + \epsilon_2 k_1 k_2 [L]^2}{1 + k_1 [L] + k_1 k_2 [L]^2} \quad (4)$$

These equations were solved for coefficients ϵ, β of the variable $[L]$ with the help of suitable auxiliary (f_1, f_2) functions and extrapolation of these to zero value of the variable.

$$\text{Thus, } f_1 = \frac{\Delta \bar{\epsilon}}{[L]} = \frac{\epsilon_1 k_1 + \epsilon_2 k_1 k_2 [L]}{1 + k_1 [L] + k_1 k_2 [L]^2}$$

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \bar{\epsilon}}{[L]} = \epsilon_1 k_1 = a_1 \quad \dots (5)$$

$a_1 = 5.50 \times 10^8$ and 1.90×10^8 for reagents I and II (Figs. 3 and 5)

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_2 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1 - a_1}{[L]} = \epsilon_2 k_1 k_2 - \epsilon_1 k_1^2 = a_2 \quad \dots (6)$$

$a_2 = -1.60 \times 10^{13}$ and -2.60×10^{12} for reagents I and II (Figs. 3 and 5).

Fig. 3. Subsidiary function f_1, f_2 as a function of free ligand concentration of Cu^{2+} complex with reagent I.

Fig. 4. ϵ, g as a function of reciprocal of free ligand concentration of Cu^{2+} complex with reagent I.

Introducing a new variable Y where,

$$Y = \frac{1}{[L]}$$

and then considering eq. (4) we get

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{\epsilon_1 k_1 Y + \epsilon_2 k_1 k_2}{Y^2 + k_1 Y + k_1 k_2}$$

$$\lim_{[Y] \rightarrow 0} \bar{\epsilon} = \epsilon_2 = b_1 \quad \dots (7)$$

$b_1 = 1.00 \times 10^4$ and 7.00×10^3 for reagents I and II (Figs. 4 and 6).

The intercept equations were solved for coefficient k_1, k_2 when we get,

$$k_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{b_1^2 + a_1 b_2} \text{ and } k_2 = \frac{a_1^2 + a_2 b_1}{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}$$

Fig. 5. Subsidiary function f_1, f_2 as a function of free ligand concentration of Cu^{2+} complex with reagent II.

Fig. 6. ϵ, g as a function of reciprocal of free ligand concentration of Cu^{2+} complex with reagent II.

The values obtained for a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 and solving the simultaneous equations yielded the first stepwise formation constant $k_1 = 1.62 \times 10^5$ and 6.48×10^4 for reagents I and II, respectively. The second stepwise formation constant was found to be $k_2 = 4.50 \times 10^4$ and 2.14×10^4 with reagents I and II, respectively. It can be assumed from the values of k_1 and k_2 that CuL_1^+ and CuL_2 are formed simultaneously in solution. The results are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu^{2+} COMPLEXES AT $27 \pm 2^\circ$

Reagent	Leden's method			Yatsimirskii's method			Harvey-Manning's method
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_2$
I	4.96	3.64	8.60	5.21	4.65	9.86	10.65
II	4.45	3.66	8.11	4.81	4.33	9.14	8.83

References

1. I. LEDEN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 160, 188A.

2. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1955, 10, 94.
 3. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1956, 11, 2306.
 4. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and T. I. FEDOROVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1956, 1, 2301.
 5. A. E. HARVEY, JR. and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488 ; 1952, 74, 4744.
 6. H. D. PORTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 127.
 7. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938/39, 115, 332.
 8. G. H. AYRES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 652.
 9. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1956.
 10. P. JOB'S, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928 ; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 113.
 11. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.